

CLINICAL - DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA OF PROLONGED COMPRESSION SYNDROME: A CLINICAL CASE

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Abstract

The article presents a clinical case of the clinical course of prolonged compression syndrome, diagnostic criteria and complications. A brief description of this disease, prevalence, risk factors will help to reduce the impact factor on the course of the disease and effective treatment.

Keywords: clinic, syndrome, long compression, diagnosis, renal failure.

Actuality of theme. As you know, as a result of explosions, building collapses, various types of traffic accidents, bodies such as crushing, crash syndrome, compression syndrome and compartment syndrome. This syndrome is fatal and with significant prevalence of complex hemodynamic and metabolic changes over a period of time in survivors requiring active treatment.

A crush itself is considered an injury resulting from the direct physical crushing of a muscle by something heavy, and a crush syndrome (prolonged crush syndrome, also called "rhabdomyolysis") is a series of metabolic changes caused by skeletal muscle damage of this severity, which leads to a violation of the integrity of cells and the release of their contents into the circulatory system. Crush syndrome (rhabdomyolysis) is the destruction of striated muscles with damage to the muscle sarcolemma and the release of decay products into the systemic bloodstream.

In turn, compression syndrome is considered to be indirect damage to muscles due to simple slow compression of a group of muscles, which leads to ischemic damage and thus causes crushed particles to enter the blood. And the compartment syndrome is a localized rapid increase in pressure inside the muscle compartment, which inevitably leads to metabolic disorders similar to rhabdomyolysis.

Therefore, approaches to both diagnosis and treatment of this disease are extremely important and responsible.

Let us give as an example the medical history of a patient who was recently treated in the trauma department of the "Regional Clinical Hospital" in Chernivtsi.

Patient A. was admitted to the trauma department on 09/20/2023 with complaints of:

- swelling of the limb (erythematous, ischemic);

- decrease in peripheral pulse;
- nausea, vomiting;
- confusion of consciousness;
- petechiae, blisters, muscle hematomas;
- myalgia, muscle paralysis, sensory deficit;
- fever;

Objectively:

- the general condition is satisfactory,
- confusion of consciousness,
- skin manifestations - petechiae, blisters,
- muscle paralysis,
- arrhythmia.

Auscultatively - whistling wheezing on inspiration, hard breathing, tachycardia are heard.

This disease is associated with road accidents.

Associated diagnosis: Unilateral right-sided pneumonia. Acute renal failure. Sinus tachycardia.

Data of laboratory and instrumental examination methods during admission:

General blood test from 09/21/2023:

Erythrocytes - $2.7 \times 10^{12}/l$; Hb - 102 g/l; CP - 0.7; Leukocytes - $13.7 \times 10^9/l$; Eosinophils-2; Rod nuclear-2; Segment nuclear - 59; Lymphocytes - 35; Monocytes - 3, ESR 24 mm h.

General analysis of urine from 09/21/2023:

Specific gravity 1018; reaction sl. sour; protein - 1.54 g/l; no sugar detected; leukocytes - 2-3 in the field of vision, erythrocytes - 25-30 in p/z.

Biochemical blood analysis from September 21, 2023, blood sugar 5.0 mmol/l.

PRS dated 09/21/2023. - negative.

Fecal analysis for worms/worms from 09/21/2023 was not found.

X-ray of OGK from September 21, 2023, a picture of right-sided pneumonia (Fig. 1)

Electrocardiography from 09/21/2023. Sinus tachycardia. HR 105 in 1 min. (Fig. 2).

Ultrasound of the OCH from 09/21/2023. Conclusion: signs of acute renal failure.

Final clinical diagnosis:

a) main: Prolonged compression syndrome, early period (8 hours), compensated degree.

b) complications: Acute renal failure, I st., exacerbation., right-sided pneumonia.

Data of laboratory and instrumental examination methods at discharge:

General blood test from 17.10.2023:

Erythrocytes - $4.0 \times 10^{12}/l$; Nv - 129 g/l; KP - 0.9; Leukocytes - $3.9 \times 10^9/l$; Eosinophils-1; Rod nuclear-1;

Segment nuclear - 65; Lymphocytes - 30; Monocytes - 3, ESR 12 mm h.

General analysis of urine from 17.10.2023:

Specific gravity 1022; reaction sl. sour; protein - traces; sugar not detected; leukocytes - 2-3 in p/z, erythrocytes - 16-17 in p/z.

Biochemical blood analysis from 17.10.2023. blood sugar 4.8 mmol/l.

X-ray of OGK from 17.10.2023. Conclusion: signs of transferred right-sided pneumonia. (Fig. 3).

Electrocardiography from 17.10.2023. Sinus tachycardia. HR 100 in 1 min. (Fig. 4).

Ultrasound of the OCH from 17.10.2023. Conclusion: signs of acute renal failure.

Treatment carried out:

- mode 1,
 - diet 10,
 - Analgesic therapy (ketamine 0.3–0.5 mg/kg body weight IV or 1–2 mg/kg body weight IV).
 - Infusion therapy (warmed saline at 10–15 mL/kg body weight/h (total 2 L), then the rate should be reduced to 500 mL/h; sodium bicarbonate (50 mEq/L) is added every 2 or 3rd bottle with dextrose; mannitol (1–2 g/kg body weight) for 4 hours (diuresis must be maintained at the level of 8 L/day (except for the elderly) and may require an infusion of 12 L/day.) , sodium polystyrene sulfonate in a dose of 15 g/day.)
 - Antiarrhythmic therapy (panangian).
 - Metabolic therapy (corvutin, tivortin).
- These recommendations:
- D supervision of a district therapist,

- BP control, repeated ECG, ultrasound of the heart.

- Ultrasound of the kidneys, + SAS with GFR,
- X-ray examination of OGK annually,
- sidnofarm 2 mg 2 times a day - continued
- Tivortin for 1 tbsp. 1. 2 r/d,
- reosorbilact (sorbilact) 800 ml
- ascorbic acid 5% 5 ml
- Vit. B1, 6% 1 ml
- Vit. B6, 2.5% 1 ml
- Vit. B12 1 ml
- novocaine 0.1% 400-500 ml
- prednisone or hydrocortisone 30-60 mg, respectively, 2-3 times a day
- glucose 40% 20-40 ml 2-3 times a day
- antibiotics.

The described clinical case demonstrates the development of a complication after prolonged compression syndrome.

Conclusion.

1. Long-term compression syndrome is a disease whose rapid development leads to a complicated course with the development of kidney failure.

2. Cardiometabolic therapy during treatment will reduce the risk of developing cardiac pathology.

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